

Artistic Activity in the Framework of Secondary Inclusive Education in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The purpose of the research: The article reveals the parameters of artistic inclusive secondary education

Research methods: The following research methods were used: analysis, synthesis, comparison, observation and statistics.

Research results: Research has revealed insufficient coverage of children with disabilities in secondary art education in Uzbekistan

Practical application: Development of methodological manuals for the timely identification, awareness and referral of talented children to secondary educational institutions with an artistic bias.

Keywords: artistic activity, culture, disability, inclusive education, painter, school, Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan.

Background: L.S. Vygotsky, believed that artistic activity in various types of art, such as music, painting, artistic expression or theater, plays a special role in the development of mental functions, as well as in enhancing the creative manifestations of children with problems¹.

The importance of art education in the modern world, its mandatory presence in every educational program of any country, is noted in UNESCO documents. The goals and objectives of art education are outlined. Culture and art are the most important components of a comprehensive education, which ensures the complete development of the individual. The right to arts education is a universal human right of students, including people with disabilities. It is the right of every child and adolescent to develop, through artistic education, aesthetic taste, creative abilities and the skills of critical thinking and analysis inherent in a person².

Methods: The role of artistic visual activity in educational institutions at all stages of age development began to be updated thanks to the innovative ideas of artists of the Renaissance, when the academic system of art education began to actively develop. Masters Cennino Cennini, L.B. Alberti, Leonardo da Vinci, A. Durer, the Carracci brothers, Rubens, Rembrandt, Reynolds, J.L. David, later A. Ashbe, Russian teacher-artists P.P. Chistyakov, D.N. Kardovsky made a great contribution to the development of art education.

At the end of the 50s of the 19th century in the countries of the Soviet Union, teaching of fine arts was conducted according to the books of N.N. Rostovtsev. According to Rostovtsev's methodology,

¹ Art pedagogy and art therapy in special education: Textbook for universities / E.A. Medvedeva, I.Yu. Levchenko, L.N. Komissarova, T.A. Dobrovolskaya. - M.: Academy, 2001. – 248 p.

² UNESCO United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization Roadmap for Arts Education World Conference on Arts Education: Building Creativity for the 21st Century Lisbon, March 6-9, 2006 Access mode: https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000384200_rus

teaching the subject began with learning to draw lines, depict plant elements, and continued in drawing from life, depicting perspective, studying color, and analyzing reproductions of works of art. Subsequently, the development of teaching methods and programs in fine arts was carried out by such authors as V.S. Kuzin, S.P. Lomov, E.V. Shorokhov, S.E. Ignatiev and others³.

Currently, art education is included as a compulsory subject in preschool and school education programs in all CIS countries and in Uzbekistan as well. Art education according to the principle of “education through art” is carried out in preschool and general secondary education. The “art teaching” approach is implemented in secondary specialized, higher and postgraduate education⁴.

Results: Secondary professional art education can be obtained at Children's Schools of Music and Arts, specialized schools of arts and culture, specialized boarding schools (focus art and culture) under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in specialized schools and boarding schools at the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan.

Studying at the Schools of Music and Arts lasts 5 years and takes place in parallel with obtaining general secondary education. Children with special educational needs on a general basis can enter the Children's School of Music after finishing the 5th grade of a general education school, based on the results of passing creative exams⁵. Some categories of students have benefits when paying tuition, including children from low-income families. Payment for their training is made at the expense of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the limits of no more than 25% of the total number of students⁶.

In specialized boarding schools (focusing on art and culture), children can be enrolled in 1st or 5th grade based on passing creative qualifying exams. Children with disabilities have first priority if they score the same number of points on exams. Specialized schools of art and culture accept children who have completed the 9th grade of secondary school. The training lasts 2 years.

The structure of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan includes 15 specialized educational institutions and boarding schools. Among them in the city of Tashkent are the Republican Specialized Art School named after P. Benkov, the Republican Specialized School of Design, the Republican Specialized Boarding School, and the National Institute of Arts and Design named after Kamoliddin Bekhzod.

Admission to specialized art schools at Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan is carried out after graduating from the seventh grade of secondary school. Within 15% of the total number of students, children from low-income families are exempt from maintenance fees. According to the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan, in total in 2024, 30 students with special educational needs studied in secondary educational organizations at the academy.

The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation runs 4 specialized vocational schools for people with disabilities - in Tashkent, Fergana and Samarkand. In them it was possible to obtain a profession and education in the following specialties: furniture design, artistic design of doll images, electronic design, design of cultural and household products, lacquer miniatures, artistic ceramics, artistic costume design, artistic ganch and wood carving, artistic painting, artistic embroidery, artistic gold embroidery, decoration of jewelry, decoration of copper products, photography, decoration of cultural and educational institutions⁷. There are no artistic directions at this time.

³ Lykova Elena Sergeevna. “The history of the formation of the subject “Fine Arts”” Omsk Scientific Bulletin, no. 3 (129), 2014, pp. 187-190.

⁴ Art education in the CIS countries: Analytical note/Moscow State University of Culture and Arts. – M., 2013. – 48 p.

⁵ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 05/05/2016 No. 144 On approval of the regulations on children's music and art schools.

⁶ Collection of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014, No. 50, art. 590; 2015, No. 33, art. 440, No. 52, Art. 646; National Legislation Database, 05/04/2018, No. 06/18/5428/1158; National Legislation Database, 12/06/2019, No. 07/19/4544/411; 12/14/2019, No. 06/19/5894/4161; 05/27/2020, No. 07/20/4730/0670

⁷ Arts education in the Republic of Uzbekistan: building creative capacities for the 21st century Supervisor of the working team of experts Academician, Professor, Doctor of Arts A.A. Khakimov Analytical Concept Paper (Situational Analysis and Development Prospects) T., 2010.- – 59 p.

Conclusions: Statistical data received from the Ministry of Culture and the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan show that, in contrast to secondary music education, the coverage of secondary art education for children with disabilities is significantly lower. In the city of Tashkent, the number of these students does not exceed 15. The lack of benefits for the education of children with disabilities in children's music and art schools under the Ministry of Culture may be the reason for the small number of students with disabilities in these schools, as well as hinder the full acquisition of special professional knowledge in the field of art. D. Yusupov also mentioned this in 2019 in his essay “Barriers on the path to art.”

In Uzbekistan, environmental, pedagogical and psychological conditions are being created for the education of children with special educational needs in secondary school, and inclusive classes are being created. However

Special arts education remains inaccessible to children with disabilities. Teachers who specialize in the subjects of drawing and painting are not aware of the peculiarities of teaching this category of children.

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